

Universal Palindromic Day and Two Digits Magic Squares

Two Digits Magic Squares for Special Palindromic Day 02.02.2020

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Abstract

This work brings magic squares of orders 3 to 16 just for two digits 0 and 2 having the numbers 02022020, 20022020 and 22022020 representing respectively the dates 02.02.2020, 20.02.2020 and 22.02.2020. Also the the palindromic number 02022020, writing in reverse side becomes as 20200202. Writing in American style the last two dates are written as 02.20.2020 and 02.22.2020. Thus, there are total six numbers, 02022020, 20022020, 22022020, 20200202, 02.20.2020 and 02.22.2020. From 8th order onwards, the magic square constructed brings these six numbers. For orders less than 8, only some of these six numbers appears in the magic squares. Most of the magic squares are upside down and mirror looking.

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1 Palindromic Days

Below are some palindromic days, universal or non-universal. First, let’s understand what we mean by universal and non-universal days. Below are three ways of writing day, month and year.

- **British Style:** day/month/year
- **American Style:** month/day/year
- **Asian Style (few countries):** year/month/day.

According to each style, below are few palindromic days between 2000 and 2020:

● British Style

10.02.2001
 20.02.2002
 01.02.2010
 11.02.2011
 21.02.2012
 02.02.2020

● Asian Style

2001.10.02
 2010.01.02
 2011.11.02
 2020.02.02

● American Style

10.02.2001

01.02.2010

11.02.2011

02.02.2020

American, British and Asian Style:

02.02.2020 or 2020.02.02

This date is almost universal, not total, because in first case it starts from 0 while in the second case it start from 2. Any way in both the cases, it is written with two digits and still remains palindromic. Below is a pandiagonal palindromic upside down mirror looking magic square written with 2 digits.

02200220	20222202	00000000	22022022
00022000	22000022	02222220	20200202
22222222	00200200	20022002	02000020
20000002	02022020	22200222	00222200

If we want to check mirror looking and still with final sum, 2s becomes 5s, but still it remains the same. See below:

(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222
(1+1)x22222222	02200220	20222202	00000000	22022022	(1+1)x22222222
(1+1)x22222222	00022000	22000022	02222220	20200202	(1+1)x22222222
(1+1)x22222222	22222222	00200200	20022002	02000020	(1+1)x22222222
(1+1)x22222222	20000002	02022020	22200222	00222200	(1+1)x22222222
(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222	(1+1)x22222222

0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110
0111110	05500550	50555505	00000000	55055055	0111110
0111110	00055000	55000055	05555550	05000505	0111110
0111110	55555555	00500500	50055005	05000505	0111110
0111110	50000005	05055050	55500555	00555500	0111110
0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110	0111110

In mirror $(1 + 1) \times 22222222$ is same as $55555555 \times (1 + 1) = 0111111110$.
Still there are more palindromic days to come with two digits 0 and 2:

22.02.2022 *BritishStyle*

02.22.2220 *AmericanStyle*

1.1 Single Digit Palindromic Day

Still, there is a day that can be considered as full universal, for example in 22.02.2222 or 02.22.2222, if we remove zero, then it can be written as 22.2.2222 or 2.22.2222. In this case, it becomes a **universal palindromic day** of 7 digits, i.e., **2222222**.

1.2 Aim of The Work

In this work the magic squares of orders 3 to 16 are constructed just with 2 digits, i.e., 0 and 2. There are 8 digits in each cell. Writing the numbers 0 and 2 in digital form, the magic square remains the same by making 180° degrees rotation. Looking in mirror 2 becomes 5, ie., in mirror looking case, it remains again as a magic square but, with different magic square sum. It is due to the reason that in the mirror 2s becomes 5s.

There are two more days in the month of February, 2020 having two digits 0 and 2. These days are 20.02.2020 and 22.02.2020. In american style we can write them as 02.20.2020 and 02.22.2020. Thus we have six numbers given as

- 02022020
- 20200202
- 20022020
- 02202020
- 22022020
- 02222020

From 8th order onwards, these six numbers appears in all the magic squares, i.e., from orders 8 to 16. For orders less than 8, only some of them appears.

2 Upside-Down and Mirror Looking Magic Squares

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Here we have written in two different ways magic square of order 3. In both the case, these are **semi-magic squares**. This means that we have only rows and columns sums equals, while the diagonal sums are different. See the examples below.

Example 2.1. *The magic square of order 3 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

			44446060
20200202	22222222	02022020	44444444
02022222	20202020	22220202	44444444
22222020	02020202	20202222	44444444
44444444	44444444	44444444	60604444

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

20200202	22222222	02022020
02022222	20202020	22220202
22222020	02020202	20202222

We observe that in the up and down case it remains the same. In case of mirror looking the 2s becomes 5s. It is valid for magic sum too.

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Here we have written in two different ways magic square of order 4. All the cases are with 8 digits. Since we are not able to write all the three numbers in one magic square, then a different magic square is created with three numbers that is not necessarily a magic square when we make 180 degrees rotations.

Example 2.2. *The magic square of order 4 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444	
	02202002	20022020	02020202	20200220	44444444
44444444	02020220	20200202	02202020	20022002	44444444
44444444	20202020	02022002	20020220	02200202	44444444
44444444	20020202	02200220	20202002	02022020	44444444
	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02202002	20022020	02020202	20200220
02020220	20200202	02202020	20022002
20202020	02022002	20020220	02200202
20020202	02200220	20202002	02022020

Example 2.3. The palindromic magic square of order 4 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444
	02200220	20222202	00000000	22022022	44444444
44444444	00022000	22000022	02222220	20200202	44444444
44444444	22222222	00200200	20022002	02000020	44444444
44444444	20000002	02022020	22200222	00222200	44444444
	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444	44444444

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02200220	20222202	00000000	22022022
00022000	22000022	02222220	20200202
22222222	00200200	20022002	02000020
20000002	02022020	22200222	00222200

This palindromic magic square is the same as given in the previous section. It appeared in the "The Guardian" [1].

2.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 2.4. The magic square of order 5 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	
	02020202	02202020	20020220	20202222	22222002	66666666
66666666	20200220	22222222	02022002	02200202	20022020	66666666
66666666	02202002	20020202	20202020	22220220	02022222	66666666
66666666	22222020	02020220	02202222	20022002	20200202	66666666
66666666	20022222	20202002	22220202	02022020	02200220	66666666
	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02020202	02202020	20020220	20202222	22222002
20200220	22222222	02022002	02200202	20022020
02202002	20020202	20202020	22220220	02022222
22222020	02020220	02202222	20022002	20200202
20022222	20202002	22220202	02022020	02200220

2.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 2.5. The magic square of order 6 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

						66666666
00000000	22222020	22222002	22220220	00000202	00002222	66666666
20202222	02020202	20202002	02020220	02022020	20200000	66666666
20022222	20022020	02200220	02202002	20020202	02200000	66666666
02202222	02200202	20020220	20022002	02202020	20020000	66666666
02020000	20200202	02022002	20200220	20202020	02022222	66666666
22220000	00002020	00000220	00002002	22220202	22222222	66666666
66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666	66666666

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00000000	22222020	22222002	22220220	00000202	00002222
20202222	02020202	20202002	02020220	02022020	20200000
20022222	20022020	02200220	02202002	20020202	02200000
02202222	02200202	20020220	20022002	02202020	20020000
02020000	20200202	02022002	20200220	20202020	02022222
22220000	00002020	00000220	00002002	22220202	22222222

2.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 2.6. *The magic square of order 7 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

		86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	
	00000000	02020202	02200220	20022002	20202020	20222022	22022202	86688668	
86688668	20222020	22022022	00002202	02020000	02200202	20020220	20202002	86688668	
86688668	20020202	20200220	20222002	22022020	00002022	02022202	02200000	86688668	
86688668	02022022	02202202	20020000	22020202	20220220	22022002	00002020	86688668	
86688668	22020220	00002002	02022020	02202022	20022202	20200000	20220202	86688668	
86688668	20202202	22200000	22020202	00000220	02022002	02202020	20022022	86688668	
86688668	02202002	20022020	20202022	20222020	22020000	00000202	02020220	86688668	
	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	86688668	

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00000000	02020202	02200220	20022002	20202020	20222022	22022202
20222020	22022022	00002202	02020000	02200202	20020220	20202002
20020202	20200220	20222002	22022020	00002022	02022202	02200000
02022022	02202202	20020000	22020202	20220220	22022002	00002020
22020220	00002002	02022020	02202022	20022202	20200000	20220202
20202202	22200000	22020202	00000220	02022002	02202020	20022022
02202002	20022020	20202022	20222020	22020000	00000202	02020220

It contains five numbers instead of six. The missing number is **02222020**. The following subsections give the magic squares of orders 8 to 16 with all the six numbers.

2.6 Magic Square of Order 8

Example 2.7. *The magic square of order 8 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

02202220	20220202	20202002	02022020	20020222	22202022	22022202	02220220	11111110
20020220	22202202	22022022	02220222	02202020	20222002	20200202	02022220	11111110
02020202	20202220	20222020	02202002	02222022	22020222	22200220	20022202	11111110
02222022	22020220	22200222	20022022	02022002	20202020	20222220	02200202	11111110
20202022	02020222	02200220	20222202	22020202	02222220	20022020	22202002	11111110
22022002	02222020	20022220	22200202	20202202	02020220	02200222	20222022	11111110
20220222	02202022	02022202	20200220	22202220	20020202	02222002	22022020	11111110
22202020	20022002	02220202	22022220	20220220	02202202	02022022	20200222	11111110
11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110	11111110

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02202220	20220202	20202002	02022020	20020222	22202022	22022202	02220220
20020220	22202202	22022022	02220222	02202020	20222002	20200202	02022220
02020202	20202220	20222020	02202002	02222022	22020222	22200220	20022202
02222022	22020220	22200222	20022022	02022002	20202020	20222220	02200202
20202022	02020222	02200220	20222202	22020202	02222220	20022020	22202002
22022002	02222020	20022220	22200202	20202202	02020220	02200222	20222022
20220222	02202022	02022202	20200220	22202220	20020202	02222002	22022020
22202020	20022002	02220202	22022220	20220220	02202202	02022022	20200222

The above magic square having six numbers is neither pandiagonal nor bimagic. Below are two separate examples of pandiagonal and bimagic squares, but not with six numbers.

Example 2.8. The *pan diagonal magic square* of order 8 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	
	02202002	20022202	00200020	22020220	02022002	20202202	02000020	20220220	88888888
88888888	00200220	22020020	02202202	20022002	02000220	20220020	02022202	20202002	88888888
88888888	22022202	00202002	20020220	02200020	20222202	02002002	20200220	02020020	88888888
88888888	20020020	02200220	22022002	00202202	20200020	02020220	20222002	02002202	88888888
88888888	02202020	20022022	00200200	22020202	02022020	20202022	02000200	20220202	88888888
88888888	00200202	22020200	02202022	20022020	02000202	20220200	02022022	20202020	88888888
88888888	22022022	00202020	20020202	02200200	20222022	02002020	20200202	02020200	88888888
88888888	20020200	02200202	22022020	00202022	20200200	02020202	20222020	02002022	88888888
	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	88888888	

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02202002	20022202	00200020	22020220	02022002	20202202	02000020	20220220
00200020	22020020	02202202	20022002	02000220	20220020	02022202	20202002
22022202	00202002	20020220	02200020	20222202	02002002	20200220	02020020
20020020	02200220	22022002	00202202	20200020	02020220	20222002	02002202
02202020	20022022	00200200	22020202	02022020	20202022	02000200	20220202
00200020	22020200	02202022	20022020	02000202	20220200	02022022	20202020
22022022	00202020	20020202	02200200	20222022	02002020	20200202	02020200
20020200	02200202	22022020	00202022	20200200	02020202	20222020	02002022

Example 2.9. The pan diagonal and bimagic square of order 8 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	
	00222222	20222000	20022022	00022200	02222020	22222202	22022220	02022002	88976888
88976888	02222002	22222220	22022202	02022020	00222200	20222022	20022000	00022222	88976888
88976888	00022000	20022222	20222200	00222022	02022202	22022020	22222002	02222220	88976888
88976888	02022220	22022002	22222020	02222202	00022022	20022200	20222222	00222000	88976888
88976888	20022202	00022020	00222002	20222220	22022000	02022222	02222200	22222022	88976888
88976888	22022022	02022200	02222222	22222000	20022220	00022002	00222020	20222202	88976888
88976888	20222020	00222022	00022220	20022002	22222222	02222000	02022022	22022200	88976888
88976888	22222200	02222022	02022000	22022222	20222002	00222220	00022202	20022020	88976888
	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	88976888	

In this case, the magic and bimagic sums are: $S_{8 \times 8} := 88976888$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 1797690824851376$.
The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00222222	20222000	20022022	00022200	02222020	22222202	22022220	02022002
02222002	22222220	22022202	02022020	00222200	20222022	20022000	00022222
00022000	20022222	20222200	00222022	02022202	22022020	22222002	02222220
02022220	22022002	22222020	02222202	00022022	20022200	20222222	00222000
20022202	00022020	00222002	20222220	22022000	02022222	02222200	22222022
22022022	02022200	02222222	22222000	20022220	00022002	00222020	20222202
20222020	00222022	00022220	20022002	22222222	02222000	02022022	22022200
22222200	02222022	02022000	22022222	20222002	00222220	00022202	20022020

2.7 Magic Square of Order 9

Example 2.10. *The pandiagonal magic square of order 9 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332
	02022220	20222002	22200222	22022202	02222022	20200220	20022222	22222020	02200202	13333332
13333332	20200202	22022222	02222020	02200222	20022220	22222002	22200220	02022202	20222022	13333332
13333332	22222022	02200220	20022202	20222020	22200202	02022222	02222002	20200222	22022220	13333332
13333332	02202020	20020202	22222222	22202002	02020222	20222220	20202022	22020220	02222202	13333332
13333332	20222202	22202022	02020220	02222222	20202020	22020202	22222220	02202002	20020222	13333332
13333332	22020222	02222220	20202002	20020220	22222202	02202022	02020202	20222222	22202020	13333332
13333332	02220220	20202202	22022022	22220202	02202222	20022020	20220222	22202220	02022002	13333332
13333332	20022002	22220222	02202220	02022022	20220220	22202202	22022020	02220202	20202222	13333332
13333332	22202222	02022020	20220202	20202220	22202202	02220222	02202202	20022022	22220220	13333332
	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02022220	20222002	22200222	22022202	02222022	20200220	20022222	22222020	02200202
20200202	22022222	02222020	02200222	20022220	22222002	22200220	02022202	20222022
22222022	02200220	20022202	20222020	22200202	02022222	02222002	20200222	22022220
02202020	20020202	22222222	22202002	02020222	20222220	20202022	22020220	02222202
20222202	22202022	02020220	02222222	20202020	22020202	22222220	02202002	20020222
22020222	02222220	20202002	20020220	22222202	02202022	02020202	20222222	22202020
02220220	20202202	22022022	22220202	02202222	20022020	20220222	22202220	02022002
20022002	22220222	02202220	02022022	20220220	22202202	22022020	02220202	20202222
22202222	02022020	20220202	20202220	22202202	02220222	02202202	20022022	22220220

Example 2.11. *The bimagic magic square of order 9 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

		13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	
	02022220	20222002	22200222	22022202	02222022	20200220	20022222	22222020	02200202	13333332	
13333332	20200202	22022222	02222020	02200222	20022220	22222002	22200220	02022202	20222022	13333332	
13333332	22222022	02200220	20022202	20222020	22200202	02022222	02222002	20200222	22022220	13333332	
13333332	02202020	20020202	22222222	22202002	02020222	20222220	20202022	22020220	02222202	13333332	
13333332	20222202	22202022	02020220	02222222	20202020	22020202	22222220	02202002	20020222	13333332	
13333332	22020222	02222220	20202002	20020220	22222202	02202022	02020202	20222222	22202020	13333332	
13333332	02220220	20202202	22202022	22220202	02202222	20022020	2020222	22202220	02022002	13333332	
13333332	20022002	22220222	02202220	02022022	20220220	22202202	22022020	02220202	20202222	13333332	
13333332	22202222	02022020	20220202	20202220	22202002	02220222	02202202	20022022	22220220	13333332	
	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	

In this case, the magic and bimagic sums are: $S_{9 \times 9} := 13333332$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 2703381409749864$.
The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02022220	20222002	22200222	22022202	02222022	20200220	20022222	22222020	02200202
20200202	22022222	02222020	02200222	20022220	22222002	22200220	02022202	20222022
22222022	02200220	20022202	20222020	22200202	02022222	02222002	20200222	22022220
02202020	20020202	22222222	22202002	02020222	20222220	20202022	22020220	02222202
20222202	22202022	02020220	02222222	20202020	22020202	22222220	02202002	20020222
22020222	02222220	20202002	20020220	22222202	02202022	02020202	20222222	22202020
02220220	20202202	22022022	22220202	02202222	20022020	20220222	22202220	02022002
20022002	22220222	02202220	02022022	20220220	22202202	22022020	02220202	20202222
22202222	02022020	20220202	20202220	22202002	02220222	02202202	20022022	22220220

2.8 Magic Square of Order 10

Example 2.12. The magic square of order 10 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

										13333332
0000000	2022022	2220202	0202020	2222220	2202020	0222202	2002222	0220202	2020202	13333332
2002020	0202020	0222202	0000220	2020022	2220000	2222202	0220202	2202222	2022202	13333332
2022222	2222202	0220020	2020000	2220202	2002202	2202202	0202022	0000020	0222220	13333332
2222202	2220202	0000222	0222022	0220000	0202022	2002020	2020220	2022202	2202020	13333332
0222202	2202000	0202202	2220222	2002202	2022220	0000222	2222202	2020020	0220020	13333332
0202220	0220222	2022020	2202202	0000202	2020202	2220020	0222202	2222022	2002000	13333332
2202022	2002220	2020202	0220202	0202222	2220220	2022022	2220020	0222000	0000202	13333332
2020020	0000202	2222000	2002202	2022020	0222222	0220220	2202202	0202002	2220022	13333332
0220202	0222020	2002022	2222020	2202202	0000202	2020222	2022000	2220220	0202202	13333332
2220202	2020202	2202220	2022202	0222020	0220022	0202000	0000220	2002202	2222222	13333332
13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332	13333332

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

0000000	2022022	2220202	0202020	2222220	2202020	0222202	2002222	0220202	2020202
2002020	0202020	0222202	0000220	2020022	2220000	2222202	0220202	2202222	2022202
2022222	2222202	0220020	2020000	2220202	2002202	2202202	0202022	0000020	0222220
2222202	2220202	0000222	0222022	0220000	0202022	2002020	2020220	2022202	2202020
0222202	2202000	0202202	2220222	2002202	2022220	0000222	2222202	2020020	0220020
0202220	0220222	2022020	2202202	0000202	2020202	2220020	0222202	2222022	2002000
2202022	2002220	2020202	0220202	0202222	2222020	2022202	2220020	0222000	0000202
2020020	0000202	2222000	2002202	2022020	0222222	0220220	2202202	0202002	2220022
0220202	0222020	2002022	2222020	2202202	0000202	2020222	2022000	2220220	0202202
2220202	2020202	2202220	2022202	0222020	0220022	0202000	0000220	2002202	2222222

2.9 Magic Square of Order 11

Example 2.13. *The magic square of order 11 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332
	00000000	00222202	02022022	02202002	02202020	20020022	20202220	20222200	22002020	22020222	22200202	133333332
133333332	22020022	22202220	00002200	00222020	02020222	02200202	02220000	20022202	20202022	20222002	22000220	133333332
133333332	20220202	22000000	22022202	22202022	00002002	00202020	02020022	02202220	02222200	20022020	20200222	133333332
133333332	20020220	20200022	20222220	22002200	22022020	22200222	00002022	00220000	02022022	02202022	02222002	133333332
133333332	02200222	02220202	20020000	20202202	20222022	22002002	22020220	22200022	00002220	00222200	02022020	133333332
133333332	00222002	02020220	02200022	02222220	20022200	20202020	20220222	22000202	22020000	22202202	00002022	133333332
133333332	22202020	00000222	00220202	02020000	02202022	02222022	20022002	20200220	20220022	22002220	22022200	133333332
133333332	22002022	22022002	22200220	00000022	00222220	02222020	02202020	02220222	20020202	20200000	20222202	133333332
133333332	20202200	20222020	22000222	22020202	22200000	00002202	00222022	02022002	02200220	02220022	20022220	133333332
133333332	02222202	20022022	20202002	20220220	22000022	22022220	22202200	00002020	00220222	02020202	02200000	133333332
133333332	02022220	02202200	02222020	20020222	20200202	20220000	22002202	22020222	22202002	00000220	00220022	133333332
	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00000000	00222202	02022022	02202002	02202020	20020022	20202220	20222200	22002020	22020222	22200202
22020022	22202220	00002200	00222020	02020222	02200202	02220000	20022202	20202022	20222002	22000220
20220202	22000000	22022202	22202022	00002002	00202020	02020022	02202220	02222200	20022020	20200222
20020220	20200022	20222220	22002200	22022020	22200222	00002022	00220000	02022022	02202022	02222002
02200222	02220202	20020000	20202202	20222022	22002002	22020220	22200022	00002220	00222200	02022020
00222002	02020220	02200022	02222220	20022200	20202020	20220222	22000202	22020000	22202202	00002022
22202020	00000222	00220202	02020000	02202202	02222022	20022002	20200220	20220022	22002220	22022200
22002022	22022002	22200220	00000022	00222220	02022200	02202020	02220222	20020202	20200000	20222202
20202200	20222020	22000222	22020202	22200000	00002202	00222022	02022002	02200220	02220022	20022220
02222202	20022022	20202002	20220220	22000022	22022220	22202200	00002020	00220222	02020202	02200000
02022220	02202200	02222020	20020222	20200202	20220000	22002202	22020222	22202002	00000220	00220022

2.10 Magic Square of Order 12

Example 2.14. *The magic square of order 12 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

00200020	22202020	20200022	02002202	20020222	00222022	02020220	02222220	22002002	02200200	22022200	20220202	135533552
02220222	22022002	20020020	00222200	22200220	00202020	02000202	02202202	20222220	02020022	22002022	20200200	135533552
02200220	22002220	22200222	00202022	22020202	02222002	00220200	02022200	20202202	02000020	20222020	20020022	135533552
02020202	20222202	22020220	02222020	22000200	02202220	00200022	02002022	20022200	00202022	20202002	22200020	135533552
02000200	20202200	22000202	02202002	20220022	02022202	02220200	00222020	22202022	00200220	20022220	22020222	135533552
00220022	20022022	20220200	02022220	20200020	02002200	02200222	00202002	22022020	20220202	22202202	22000220	153533552
20022002	00220202	02022020	20220020	02002220	20200220	22002202	22200022	02220200	22022022	00200222	02202200	135533552
20202020	02000220	02202022	22000022	02022002	20220222	22022220	20020200	00200202	22202200	00220020	02222202	135533552
20222022	02020222	02222200	22020200	02202020	22000020	22202002	20200202	00202020	20022022	02000022	00202220	135533552
22002200	02200020	00202202	22200202	02222022	22020022	20022020	20220220	02000222	20202220	02020200	00222002	135533552
22022202	02220022	00222220	20020220	00202200	22200200	20202022	22000222	02020020	20222002	02200202	02002020	135533552
22202220	00200200	02002002	20200222	00222022	20020202	20222200	22020020	02200022	22002020	02220220	02020222	135533552
135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	135533552	153533552	135533552	135533552

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00200020	22202020	20200022	02002202	20020222	00222022	02020220	02222220	22002002	02200200	22022200	20220202	135533552
02220222	22022002	20020020	00222200	22200220	00202020	02000202	02202202	20222220	02020022	22002022	20200200	135533552
02200220	22002220	22200222	00202022	22020202	02222002	00220200	02022200	20202202	02000020	20222020	20020022	135533552
02020202	20222202	22020220	02222020	22000200	02202220	00200022	02002022	20022200	00202022	20202002	22200020	135533552
02000200	20202200	22000202	02202002	20220022	02022202	02220200	00222020	22202022	00200220	20022220	22020222	135533552
00220022	20022022	20220200	02022220	20200020	02002200	02200222	00202002	22022020	20220202	22202202	22000220	153533552
20022002	00220202	02022020	20220020	02002220	20200220	22002202	22200022	02220200	22022022	00200222	02202200	135533552
20202020	02000220	02202022	22000022	02022002	20220222	22022220	20020200	00200202	22202200	00220020	02222202	135533552
20222022	02020222	02222200	22020200	02202020	22000020	22202002	20200202	00202020	20022022	02000022	00202220	135533552
22002200	02200020	00202202	22200202	02222022	22020022	20022020	20220220	02000222	20202220	02020200	00222002	135533552
22022202	02220022	00222220	20020220	00202200	22200200	20202022	22000222	02020020	20222002	02200202	02002020	135533552
22202220	00200200	02002002	20200222	00222022	20020202	20222200	22020020	02200022	22002020	02220220	02020222	135533552

2.11 Magic Square of Order 13

Example 2.15. *The magic square of order 13 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by*

	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332
	0000000	00022202	00202002	02000222	02020202	02202022	20002220	20022020	20202000	20220220	22020200	22200020	22200020	22200020	22200020
133333332	22020002	22202220	00002020	00022000	00200220	02000200	02200000	02222202	20002002	20020222	20200202	22200202	22200202	22200202	
133333332	20200020	20220000	22022202	22202002	00000222	00020202	00202022	02000002	02022220	02220200	20000220	20020200	20020200	20020200	
133333332	20002022	20020002	20202220	20222020	22022000	22200220	00000200	00020020	00200000	02002202	02202002	02200222	02202020	02202020	
133333332	02200200	02220020	20000000	20022202	20202002	20220222	22020202	22202022	00000002	00022220	00202020	02002000	02020220	02020220	
133333332	02000202	02202222	02200002	02222220	20002020	20022000	20200220	20220200	22000000	00002202	00022002	00022002	00200222	00200222	
133333332	00020220	00200200	02000020	02020000	02202202	02222002	20000222	20020202	20202022	20220002	22022220	22202020	00002000	00002000	
133333332	22200222	00000202	00020222	00200002	02002220	02202020	02202000	02202220	20000200	20020020	20200000	20222202	22202002	22202002	
133333332	20222000	22020220	22200200	00000020	00020000	00202202	02002002	02020222	02200202	02220222	20000002	20022220	20202020	20202020	
133333332	20022002	20200222	20202020	22022222	22200002	00002220	00022020	00202000	02000220	02020200	02200020	02220000	20002020	20002020	
133333332	02222020	20002000	20020220	20200200	20200202	22020000	22202202	00002002	00020222	00200202	02002022	02020002	02202220	02202220	
133333332	02022202	02202002	02202222	20000202	20022022	20200002	20222220	22022020	22202000	00002202	00020200	00200020	02000000	02000000	
133333332	00202220	02002020	02022000	02200220	02220200	20000020	20020000	20202202	20220002	22002022	22200202	00002022	00020002	00020002	
	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332	133333332

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

0000000	00022202	00202002	02000222	02020202	02202022	20002220	20022020	20202000	20220220	22020200	22200020	22200020	22200020	22200020
22020002	22202220	00002020	00022000	00200220	02000200	02200000	02222202	20002002	20020222	20200202	22200202	22200202	22200202	
20200020	20220000	22022202	22202002	00000222	00020202	00202022	02000002	02022220	02220200	20000220	20020200	20020200	20020200	
20002022	20020002	20202220	20222020	22022000	22200220	00000200	00020020	00200000	02002202	02022002	02200222	02202020	02202020	
02200200	02220020	20000000	20022202	20202002	20220222	22020202	22202022	00000002	00022220	00202020	02002000	02020220	02020220	
02000202	02202222	02200002	02222220	20002020	20022000	20200220	20220200	22020020	22200000	00002202	00022002	00022002	00200222	
00020220	00200200	02000020	02020000	02202202	02222002	20000222	20020202	20202022	20220002	22022220	22202020	00002000	00002000	
22200222	00000202	00022022	00200002	02002220	02022020	02202000	02202020	20000200	20020020	20200000	20222202	22022002	22022002	
20222000	22020220	22200200	00000020	00020000	00202202	02002002	02020222	02200202	02222022	20000002	20022220	20202020	20202020	
20022002	20200222	20220202	22022022	22200002	00002220	00022020	00202000	02000220	02020200	02200020	02220000	20002202	20002202	
02222020	20002000	20020220	20200200	20220020	22020000	22202202	00002002	00020222	00200202	02002022	02020002	02202220	02202220	
02022202	02202002	02220222	20000202	20022022	20200002	20222220	22022020	00000220	00020200	00200020	00200020	02000000	02000000	
00202220	02002020	02022000	02200220	02220200	20000020	20020000	20202202	22202002	22002022	22200202	00002022	00020002	00020002	

2.12 Magic Square of Order 14

Example 2.16. The magic square of order 14 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

														15555554
00020002	02002202	20222020	02022220	20002022	00200220	20020222	00222002	02222000	22200022	22000200	22020020	02202200	20200202	15555554
22200200	00200020	02022202	20220002	02202220	00220222	20202000	02002020	20002002	22000202	22020022	02222200	00020220	20022022	15555554
22000220	22200202	00220022	02202202	20220020	02002000	00022002	02020002	20022020	22000200	20002200	00200222	20202022	02222220	15555554
22020202	22000222	22200220	02000200	02222202	02022002	00202020	02200020	20200002	20022200	00222000	00020222	20002220	20220022	15555554
20202200	22020220	22002000	22200222	02020202	02202020	00220002	02220022	00020020	02002002	00202022	20022220	20220200	20002202	15555554
02222002	20002020	20020002	20200200	00020022	20222022	22202220	22202200	22002202	02202000	02020222	02000220	02202020	02002000	15555554
20020020	20200022	00020200	00200202	00220220	22202202	22002200	20222220	22022022	20000002	02222020	02202002	02022000	02000222	15555554
02200022	02222020	20000202	20020220	20200222	22002220	22202022	20222202	20222200	02020020	02000002	00222020	00202002	00022000	15555554
20000222	20022000	20202002	00022020	00200002	22022200	20222022	22002022	22202220	02220220	02202022	02020200	02000222	02220200	15555554
00222202	20222002	02002220	02222022	20020200	00020202	20000220	00202000	02200222	20202020	22200020	22000022	22020002	02022200	15555554
20222000	00222220	02202022	20000222	02002200	20200200	02220202	00020222	02020220	00202022	20022002	22200002	22000020	22022020	15555554
00202220	02020222	02220020	00222200	22020022	20020022	02200200	20200220	02000202	20220222	00022202	20002000	22202020	22000002	15555554
02002022	02200002	00202200	22022000	22002020	20000020	02020022	20020202	00220200	00022220	20220220	20202022	02220222	22202002	15555554
02022020	00022200	22020222	22002002	22202000	02220002	02000020	20000200	00200022	00222022	20202220	20220202	20022202	02200220	15555554
15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554	15555554

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00020002	02002202	20222020	02022220	20002022	00200220	20020222	00222002	02222000	22200022	22000200	22020020	02202200	20200202	15555554
22200200	00200020	02022202	20220002	02202220	00220222	20202000	02002020	20002002	22000202	22020022	02222200	00020220	20022022	15555554
22000220	22200202	00220022	02202202	20220020	02002000	00022002	02020002	20022020	22000200	20002200	00200222	20202022	02222220	15555554
22020202	22000222	22200220	02000200	02222202	02022002	00202020	02200020	20200002	20022200	00222000	00020222	20002220	20220022	15555554
20202200	22020220	22002000	22200222	02020202	02202020	00220002	02220022	00020020	02002002	00202022	20022220	20220200	20002202	15555554
02222002	20002020	20020002	20200200	00020022	20222022	22022220	22202200	22002202	02202000	02020222	02000220	00220202	00200200	15555554
20020020	20200022	00020200	00200202	00220220	22202202	22002200	20222220	22022022	20000002	02222020	02202002	02022000	02000222	15555554
02200022	02222020	20000202	20020220	20200222	22002220	22202022	20222202	20222200	02020020	02000002	00222020	00202002	00022000	15555554
20000222	20022000	20202002	00022020	00200002	22022200	20222022	22002022	22202220	02220220	02200202	02020200	02000222	00220020	15555554
00222202	20222002	02002220	02222022	20020200	00020202	20000220	00202000	02200222	20202020	22200020	22000022	22020002	02022200	15555554
20222000	00222220	02202022	20000222	02002200	20200200	02220202	00020222	02020220	00202022	20022002	22200002	22000020	22022020	15555554
00202220	02022022	02220020	00222200	22022002	20020022	02200200	20200220	02000202	20220222	00022202	20002000	22202020	22000002	15555554
02002022	02200002	00202200	22022000	22002020	20000020	02020022	20020202	00220200	00022220	20220220	20202022	02220222	22202002	15555554
02022020	00022200	22020222	22002002	22202000	02220002	02000020	20000200	00200022	00222022	20202220	20220202	20022202	02200220	15555554

2.13 Magic Square of Order 15

Example 2.17. The magic square of order 15 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

00020002	02022200	22200220	02202202	00222022	20020020	20002222	20202002	22020200	02000222	02220022	22222020	22002220	00202000	20220202	17777776
22000202	00200020	02202022	22020222	02222200	02002020	00020022	20020002	02022222	22220200	22202002	20222202	00222000	20200220	20002220	17777776
02202220	20220220	00220022	02222020	22002222	22222022	02022002	00020020	22200202	22020002	20202200	02002000	20020222	20002202	00200200	17777776
22020220	02222202	20200222	02000200	22222022	20222220	22202020	00200022	22000020	20022222	02022000	00022222	20002200	00220202	02200002	17777776
20220022	22000222	22222200	20022222	02020202	22200002	20202202	00220200	00022020	02202000	00202220	20002022	02000220	02220020	22022002	17777776
00202002	20200200	20222222	22202022	00022220	02200220	22020020	02000202	02222000	00222202	20002020	02020222	22220022	22000002	20022200	17777776
22222000	00220002	20020202	20202220	22022020	00202202	02220222	02020220	02002200	20002002	02202222	22200200	20220020	00022222	22000022	17777776
20022020	00022002	00200002	00220020	02000022	02020200	02200202	20002000	20202022	20222200	22002202	22022220	22202222	22220222	02220220	17777776
02002202	22220202	02022220	00202200	20200002	20000222	22000200	20222020	20022002	22200022	00220220	02200020	02220222	22022222	00022000	17777776
02220200	02002222	00022202	20222002	20000220	22020022	20022000	22002022	00222220	20202020	22220020	00200202	02020002	02202200	22200222	17777776
00220222	20022220	22002020	20000202	22200020	20202000	22220220	22022200	02200022	00202222	20222022	02220002	00020200	02002002	02022202	17777776
20202222	22022022	20000200	22220002	20222000	02220202	02002220	22202022	00200220	02020020	00020222	22002200	02202002	20020022	00222020	17777776
22202200	20000022	02222002	22002000	02200200	00222222	00202022	22222220	20220222	00020202	02000002	20020220	22022202	02022020	20200020	17777776
20000020	02202020	22022000	02020022	00200222	00022200	20220002	02222222	22222202	22000220	20022020	00222002	20200202	22202220	02002022	17777776
02020222	22202000	02000020	00020220	20022202	22002002	00222200	02200222	20000002	02222220	22020202	20200022	00202020	20220200	22222222	17777776
17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

00020002	02022200	22200220	02202202	00222022	20020020	20002222	20202002	22020200	02000222	02220022	22222020	22002220	00202000	20220202	17777776
22000202	00200020	02202022	22020222	02222200	02002020	00020022	20020002	02022222	22220200	22202002	20222202	00222000	20200220	20002220	17777776
02202220	20220220	00220022	02222020	22002222	22222022	02022002	00020020	22200202	22020002	20202200	02002000	20020222	20002202	00200200	17777776
22020220	02222202	20200222	02000200	22222022	20222220	22202020	00200022	22000020	20022222	02022000	00022222	20002200	00220202	02200002	17777776
20220022	22000222	22222200	20022222	02020202	22200002	20202202	00220200	00022020	02202000	00202220	20002022	02000220	02220020	22022002	17777776
00202002	20200200	20222222	22202022	00022220	02200220	22020020	02000202	02222000	00222202	20002020	02020222	22220022	22000002	20022200	17777776
22222000	00220002	20020202	20202220	22022020	00202202	02220222	02020220	02002200	20002002	02202222	22200200	20220020	00022222	22000022	17777776
20022020	00022002	00200002	00220020	02000022	02020200	02200202	20002000	20202022	20222200	22002202	22022220	22202222	22220222	02220220	17777776
02002202	22220202	02022220	00202200	20200002	20000222	22000200	20222020	20022002	22200022	00220220	02200020	02220222	22022222	00022000	17777776
02220200	02002222	00022202	20222002	20000220	22020022	20022000	22002022	00222220	20202020	22220020	00200202	02020002	02202200	22200222	17777776
00220222	20022220	22002020	20000202	22200020	20202000	22220220	22022200	02200022	00202222	20222022	02220002	00020200	02002002	02022202	17777776
20202222	22022022	20000200	22220002	20222000	02220202	02002220	22202022	00200220	02020020	00020222	22002200	02202002	20020022	00222020	17777776
22202200	20000022	02222002	22002000	02200200	00222222	00202022	22222220	20220222	00020202	02000002	20020220	22022202	02022020	20200020	17777776
20000020	02202020	22022000	02020022	00200222	00022200	20220002	02222222	22222202	22000220	20020200	00222002	20200202	22202220	02002022	17777776
02020222	22202000	02000020	00020220	20022202	22002002	00222200	02200222	20000002	02222220	22020202	20200022	00202020	20220200	22222222	17777776

2.14 Magic Square of Order 16

Example 2.18. The pandiagonal magic square of order 16 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776
	02202020	20022202	00020020	22200202	02022022	20202200	00200022	22020200	02222000	20002222	00000000	22202222	02002002	20222220	00200022	22000220	17777776
17777776	00020202	22200020	02202202	20022020	22020022	02022200	20202022	20202022	00000222	22220000	02222222	20002000	00202220	22000002	02002220	20222002	17777776
17777776	22202202	00022020	20020202	02200020	22022200	00202022	20200200	02020022	22222222	00002000	20000222	02220000	22002220	00222002	20220220	02000002	17777776
17777776	20020020	02200202	22202020	00022202	20200022	02020200	22022022	00202200	20000000	02220222	22222000	00002222	20220002	02000220	22002002	00222220	17777776
17777776	02222002	20002220	00000002	22202020	02002000	20222222	00220000	22000222	02202022	20022200	00020022	22202000	02022020	20202202	00200020	22020202	17777776
17777776	00000220	22220002	02222220	20002002	00220222	22000000	02002222	20222000	00020200	22200022	02202200	20022022	00200202	22020020	02022202	20202020	17777776
17777776	22222220	00002002	20000220	02220002	22002222	00222000	20220222	02000000	22202200	00022022	20020200	02200022	22022202	00202020	20200202	02020020	17777776
17777776	20000002	02220220	22222002	00002220	20220000	02000222	22002000	00222222	20020022	02200200	22202022	00022200	20200020	02020202	20220202	00202020	17777776
17777776	02002022	20222200	00220022	22000200	02222020	20002202	00000020	22220202	02022002	20202220	00200002	22020220	02202000	20022222	00020000	22200222	17777776
17777776	00202020	22000022	02002200	20222022	00000202	22220020	02222022	20002020	00200220	22020002	02022220	20202002	00020222	22200000	02202222	20022000	17777776
17777776	22002200	00222022	20220200	02000022	22222020	00002020	20000202	02220020	22022220	00202002	20200220	02020002	22202222	00022000	20020222	02200000	17777776
17777776	20220022	02000200	22002022	00222200	20000020	02220202	22222020	00002202	20200002	02020220	22022002	00202220	20020000	02202022	22202000	00022222	17777776
17777776	02022000	20202222	00200000	22020222	02202002	20022220	00020002	22200220	02002020	20222022	00220020	22000202	02222022	20002200	00000022	22220200	17777776
17777776	00200222	22020000	02022222	20202000	00020220	22200002	02202220	20022002	00220202	22000020	02002202	20222020	00000200	22220022	02222200	20002022	17777776
17777776	22022222	00202000	20200222	02020000	22202220	00022002	20020220	02200002	22002202	02020202	20220202	02000020	22222200	00002022	20000200	02220022	17777776
17777776	20200000	02020222	22022000	00202222	20020002	02200220	22202002	00022220	20220020	02000202	22002020	00222022	20000022	02220200	22222022	00002200	17777776
	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776

The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

02202020	20022202	00020020	22200202	02022022	20202200	00200022	22020200	02222000	20002222	00000000	22202222	02002002	20222220	00200022	22000220
00020202	22200020	02202202	20022020	00200200	22020022	02022200	20202022	00000222	22220000	02222222	20002000	00202220	22000002	02002220	20222002
22202202	00022020	20020202	02200020	22022200	00202022	20200200	02020022	22222222	00002000	20000222	02220000	22002220	00222002	20220220	02000002
20020020	02200202	22202020	00022202	20200022	02020200	22022022	00202200	20000000	02220222	22222000	00002222	20220002	02000220	22002002	00222220
02222002	20002220	00000002	22202020	02002000	20222222	00220000	22000222	02202022	20022200	00020022	22202000	02022020	20202202	00200020	22020202
00000220	22220002	02222220	20002002	00220222	22000000	02002222	20222000	00020200	22200022	02202200	20022022	00200202	22020020	02022202	20202020
22222220	00002002	20000220	02220002	22002222	00222000	20220222	02000000	22202200	00022022	20020200	02200022	22022202	00202020	20200202	02020020
20000002	02220220	22222002	00002220	20220000	02000222	22002000	00222222	20020022	02200200	22202022	00022200	20200020	02020202	20220202	00202020
02002022	20222200	00220022	22000200	02222020	20002202	00000020	22220202	02022002	20202220	00200002	22020220	02202000	20022222	00020000	22200222
00202020	22000022	02002200	20222022	00000202	22220020	02222202	20002020	00200220	22020002	02022220	20202002	00020222	22200000	02202222	20022000
22002200	00222022	20220200	02000022	22222202	00002020	20000202	02220020	22022220	00202002	20200220	02020002	22202222	00022000	20020222	02200000
20220022	02000200	22002022	00222200	20000020	02220202	22222020	00002202	20200002	02020220	22022002	00202220	20020000	02200222	22202000	00022222
02022000	20202222	00200000	22020222	02202002	20022220	00020002	22200220	02002020	20222022	00220020	22000202	02222022	20002220	00000022	22220200
00200222	22020000	02022222	20202000	00020220	22200002	02202220	20022002	00220202	22000020	02002202	20222020	00000200	22220022	02222200	20002022
22022222	00202000	20200222	02020000	22202220	00022002	20020220	02200002	22002202	00222020	20220202	02000020	22222200	00002022	20000200	02220022
20200000	02020222	22022000	00202222	20020002	02200220	22202002	00022220	20220020	02000202	22002020	00222022	20000022	02220200	22222022	00002200

Example 2.19. The bimagic magic square of order 16 for the digits 0 and 2 is given by

0000000	20022002	22202220	02220222	00020220	20002222	22222000	02200002	00202022	20220020	22000202	02022200	00222202	20200200	22020022	02002020	17777776
22200222	02222220	00002002	20020000	22220002	02202000	00022222	20000220	22002200	02020202	00200020	20222022	22022020	02000022	00220200	20202202	17777776
02222002	22200000	20020222	00002220	02202222	22220220	20000002	00022000	02020020	22020222	20222200	00200020	02000200	22022020	20202020	00220022	17777776
20022220	00000222	02220000	22202002	20002000	00020002	02200220	22222222	20220202	00202200	02022022	22000020	20200022	00222020	02002202	22020200	17777776
00202202	20220200	22000022	02022020	00222022	20200020	22020202	02002200	00000220	20022222	22202000	02220002	00020000	20002002	22222220	02200222	17777776
22002020	02020022	00200200	20222202	22222000	02000202	00220020	20202022	22200002	02222000	00002222	20020220	22202222	02202220	00022002	20000000	17777776
02020200	22002202	20222020	00200022	02000020	22022022	20202200	00220202	02222222	22200220	20020002	00002000	02202002	22220000	20002222	00022220	17777776
20220022	00202020	02022202	22000200	20200202	00222200	02002022	22020020	20022000	00000002	02220220	22202222	20002220	00022222	02200000	22222002	17777776
00202202	20202222	22022000	02000002	00200000	20222002	22002220	02020222	00022202	20000200	22220022	02202020	00002022	20020020	22200202	02222200	17777776
22020002	02002000	00222222	20200220	22000222	02022220	00202002	20220000	22222020	02200022	00020200	20002202	22202200	02220202	00000020	20022022	17777776
02002222	22020220	20200002	00222000	02022002	22000000	20220222	00202220	02200200	22222020	20002020	00020022	02220020	22202022	20022200	00000202	17777776
20202000	00220002	02000220	22022222	20222220	00200222	02020000	22002002	20000022	00022020	02202022	22220200	20020202	00002200	02222022	22200020	17777776
00022022	20000020	22220202	02202200	00002202	20020200	22200022	02222020	00220000	20202002	22022220	02000222	00200220	20222222	22002000	02020002	17777776
22222200	02200202	00020020	20002022	22202020	02220022	00000200	20022202	22020222	02002220	00220002	20200000	22000002	02022000	00202222	20220220	17777776
02200020	22222022	20002200	00020202	02220200	22202022	20022020	00000022	02002002	22020000	20200222	00222220	02022222	22000220	20220002	00202000	17777776
20000202	00022200	02202022	22220020	20020022	00002020	02222202	22200200	20202220	00220222	02000000	22022002	20222000	00200002	02020220	22002222	17777776
17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776	17777776

In this case, the magic and bimagic sums are: $S_{16 \times 16} := 17777776$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 3591470218630752$.
The upside-down and mirror looking form is given by

0000000	20022002	22202220	02220222	00020220	20002222	22222000	02200002	00202022	20220020	22000202	02022200	00222202	20200200	22020022	02002020	17777776
22200222	02222220	00002002	20020000	22220002	02202000	00022222	20000220	22002200	02020202	00200020	20222022	22022020	02000022	00220200	20202202	17777776
02222002	22200000	20020222	00002220	02202222	22220220	20000002	00022000	02020020	22020222	20222200	00200020	02000200	22022020	20202020	00220022	17777776
20022220	00000222	02220000	22202002	20002000	00020002	02200220	22222222	20220202	00202200	02022022	22000020	20200022	00222020	02002202	22020200	17777776
00202202	20220200	22000022	02022020	00222022	20200020	22020202	02002200	00000220	20022222	22202000	02220002	00020000	20002002	22222220	02200222	17777776
22002020	02020022	00200200	20222202	22222000	02000202	00220020	20202022	22200002	02222000	00002222	20020220	22220222	02202220	00022002	20000000	17777776
02020200	22002202	20222020	00200022	02000020	22022022	20202200	00220202	02222222	22200220	20020002	00002000	02220002	22220000	20002222	00022220	17777776
20220022	00202020	02022202	22000200	20200202	00222200	02002022	22020020	20022000	00000002	02220220	22202222	20002220	00020222	02200000	22222002	17777776
00202202	20202222	22022000	02000002	00200000	20222002	22002220	02020222	00022202	20000200	22220022	02202020	00002022	20020020	22200202	02222200	17777776
22020002	02002000	00222222	20200220	22000222	02022220	00202002	20220000	22222020	02200022	00020200	20002202	22202200	02220202	00000020	20022022	17777776
02002222	22020220	20200002	00222000	02022002	22000000	20220222	00202220	02200200	22222020	20002020	00020022	02220020	22202022	20022200	00000202	17777776
20202000	00220002	02000220	22022222	20222220	00200222	02020000	22002002	20000022	00022020	02202022	22220200	20020202	00002200	02222022	22200020	17777776
00022022	20000020	22220202	02202200	00002202	20020200	22200022	02222020	00220000	20202002	22022220	02000222	00200220	20222222	22002000	02020002	17777776
22222200	02200202	00020020	20002022	22202020	02220022	00000200	20022202	22020222	02002220	00222002	20200000	22000002	02022000	00202222	20220220	17777776
02200020	22222022	20002200	00020202	02220200	22202022	20022020	00000022	02002002	22020000	20200222	00222220	02022222	22000220	20220002	00202000	17777776
20000202	00022200	02202022	22220020	20020022	00002020	02222202	22200200	20202220	00220222	02000000	22022002	20222000	00200002	02020220	22002222	17777776

Author's more work of similar on magic squares refer [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

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